

**A novel Type I methanotroph *Methylomonas sedimenticola* strain WWC4:
polyphasic characterization and genome analysis**

Kumal Khatri^{1,2}, Jyoti A. Mohite^{1,2}, and Monali C. Rahalkar^{1,2*}

¹C2, Bioenergy group, MACS Agharkar Research Institute, G.G. Agarkar Road, Pune 411004,
Maharashtra, India

²Savitribai Phule Pune University, Ganeshkhind Road, Pune 411007, Maharashtra, India

Tel: +91-20-25325119

Fax: +91-20-2651542

*Corresponding author: monalirahalkar@aripune.org

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Abstract

A pure culture of methanotroph strain WWC4 was isolated from the sediment of a freshwater creek. Morphologically the methanotroph formed pink-colored round colonies and was primarily classified to be a *Methylomonas* strain. Strain WWC4 is a thick short motile rod of 2.5-3 μm long and 0.8-1.2 μm thick in size with a Gram-negative character. It is motile and forms yellowish-orange colored 2-3 mm opaque colonies on solid NMS media plates and pellicle growth in liquid medium under methane and air-rich environments. *Methylomonas* sp. WWC4 shared 74.48%, 74.76%, and 20.7 [18.5-23.2%] of AAI, ANIb, and DDH values, respectively, with *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T. The cell wall contains 15:1 ω 8c (21.09%), 16:0 3OH (15.7%), and 16:1 ω 5c (12.6%) as a major fatty acids. The GC content is 55.9 mol%. The whole-genome shotgun project was deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank, and the accession number is JAATWI0.1. The genomic evaluation and phylogenetic analysis concluded the WWC4 strain was a putative novel methanotroph species. This putative novel species was isolated from a muddy-water sample and was phylogenetically related to the *Methylomonas* genus; therefore, the name is tentatively proposed as a *Methylomonas sedimenticola* sp. nov. strain WWC4.

1. Introduction

Genus *Methylomonas* belongs to Type I methanotrophs, grows between 10-40°C temperature range and is mesophilic. The morphological feature of the genus *Methylomonas* is to form red, pink, and orange carotenoid non-water-soluble pigment colonies on solid media (Bowman 2015). The member of the genus *Methylomonas* can be found in diverse habitats, including wetland muds, sediments of freshwater lakes and rivers, activated sludge and wastewater, and coal mine drainage water (Bowman 2015). The first member of the genus *Methylomonas*, or the first methanotroph, was isolated by Söhngen in 1906 from the aquatic plant material and named *Bacillus methanicus* and later modified *Methylomonas methanica* by Orla-Jensen in 1909 (Dworkin and Foster 1956, Whittenbury R 1984). Besides *Methylomonas methanica*, *Methylomonas aurantiaca*, *Methylomonas fodinarum* (Bowman, Sly et al. 1990), *Methylomonas scandinavica* (Kalyuzhnaya, Khmelenina et al. 1999), and *Methylomonas koyamae* (Ogiso, Ueno et al. 2012) are also recognised species of the *Methylomonas* genus. *Methylomonas* strain WWC4 was isolated from Maharashtra, India is a novel species. The strain WWC4 can utilise methane and methanol as carbon sources; and ammonium chloride, glutamate, peptone, yeast extract, and lysine as nitrogen sources. Strain can grow in the absence of a soluble nitrogen source, and therefore, it can fix environmental nitrogen. It shows 97.81% 16S rRNA similarity with *Methylomonas koyamae* Fw12E-Y^T and 96.62% *pmoA* gene similarity with *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T. This isolate proposed to allocate to a novel species, *Methylomonas sedimenticola* sp. nov. The present study contains cultivation, identification, polyphasic characterisation, and genomic analysis of strain WWC4.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Sampling

A muddy sample was collected from Nagaon beach, Alibag, Maharashtra, India (18°26'30" N 72°54'20" E) and named the WWC sample. WWC sample was taken from a shallow freshwater patch of a wetland at the end of a freshwater creek region. WWC sample was collected in September 2017. In a sterile container, the environmental sample was collected and transferred to the laboratory on the same day. A minimum of three samples were taken and handled aseptically. These were processed for enrichment in methane and air-rich environments. The remaining sample was stored at 4-8°C for further experimentations.

2.2 Enrichment and isolation

The sample was diluted nine times in a sterilised sealed serum bottle containing diluted nitrate-mineral salts dNMS liquid media and methane and air (30:70) as headspace gases (Whittenbury, Phillips et al. 1970). On the 24th day of incubation of the enrichment bottle, headspace methane reduction was detected. This enriched broth was streaked on solid dNMS media plates, followed by incubation in a desiccator containing methane and air (20:80) as headspace gases. Different coloured and sized colonies appeared after 3-4 weeks of incubation. After visualisation of growth, 20µl of enrichment broth was inoculated using a streak plate technique on solid media petri-plates containing 2% agarose as a solidifying agent and incubated at 25°C in a desiccator with methane and air as headspace gas. Headspace gases were replaced weekly. Single colonies were picked using a sterilised toothpick and streaked on solid media petri-plates containing 2% agarose as a solidifying agent and incubated at 25°C in a desiccator with methane and air headspace gas.

Repetitively, single colonies were picked using a sterilised toothpick or wire-loop and streaked on a solid media petri-plate to get the axenic culture of methanotrophs that contains single methanotrophs without any heterotrophic contamination.

Purity of axenic culture was carried out by streaking on 1/10th diluted nutrient agar plate containing 1% glucose and microscopic observation. Methanotrophs are C1-utilisers. Methanotrophs do not possess the ability to utilise multi-carbon or complex carbohydrates, resulting in no growth on the nutrient agar plates.

2.3 Morphological Characterization

Morphological analysis was done by wet-mount of culture under phase-contrast microscopy and Gram-staining under light microscopy to check the Gram character of isolates. Live cells of methanotrophs strain were observed under a phase-contrast microscope (Nikon 80i, Japan microscope with a camera) under 100X magnifications with oil emulsion. The Gram character of heat-fixed culture was determined using a standard Gram-staining protocol and observed under a bright-field microscope. Bacterial culture was fixed and processed to observe under a Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Zeiss model EVO-MA-15 SEM). SEM sample preparation has been described before (Pandit, Hoppert et al. 2018).

2.4 Biochemical Characterization

Various growth parameters were checked using liquid dNMS media in a biological replicate (n=3). The utilisation of different carbon sources was studied supplemented with one of the following autoclaved (at 10psi) or filter-sterilised substrates (0.1%, w/v): formate, arabinose, lactose, xylose, fructose, formamide, raffinose, maltose, glucose, and sucrose. This experiment was conducted using a microtiter plate and incubated at 25°C. Methanol utilisation or tolerance was studied by growing the culture in a 0.2-5% range of methanol. Various nitrogen source was studied using a microtiter plate containing liquid dNMS (without KNO₃) supplemented with one of the following autoclaved (at 10psi) substrates (0.05%, w/v): NH₄Cl, urea, glycine, serine, valine, asparagine, aspartate, L-glutamic acid, glutamate, peptone, and yeast extract. The culture was also grown in a range of pH with and without buffer-condition. Citrate-phosphate buffer (pH 3–6.8) and glycine buffer (pH 8, 9, and 9.6) were used for buffering the

dNMS-medium. Without buffer conditions, only HCl or NaOH was used to adjust the pH from pH 3 to pH 10. The plate was incubated in glass desiccators containing around ~30% methane gas in the headspace as carbon source and rest air. The desiccators were incubated at 25°C. The optimum temperature range (10-40°C) was studied in sterilized sealed 35ml serum bottles containing 9ml dNMS media.

2.5 DNA Extraction and Sequencing

Identification of methanotrophs was carried out by amplifying the functional *pmoA* gene or molecular marker of methanotrophs (Wen, Yang et al. 2016). After confirmation of methanotrophic culture by functional *pmoA* gene amplification, culture was repetitively streaked to get axenic culture. Then 16S rRNA gene amplification was carried out using axenic culture of methanotrophs.

Particulate methane monooxygenase β subunit (*pmoA* gene) and 16S rRNA gene amplification were carried out using A189f-mb661r and 27f-1492r primers, respectively, using direct colonies (in case of *pmoA* amplification) or extracted DNA (for both *pmoA* and 16S rRNA gene amplification). First Base Laboratories, Malaysia, did the sequencing of amplified products. The sequences obtained were subjected to BLAST analysis. The alignment of sequences was done using the MAFFT alignment server (<https://mafft.cbrc.jp/alignment/server/>). Based on cut-off values of 98.65% for the 16S rRNA gene (Rossi-Tamisier, Benamar et al. 2015) and a corresponding cut-off value of 87% for the *pmoA* gene nucleotide sequence, the strains were designated to belong to putative novel species (Kim, Han et al. 2008, Wen, Yang et al. 2016). The cut-off value for the *pmoA* gene nucleotide sequence is 84% (Dedysh, Didriksen et al. 2015), and the 16S rRNA gene is 94.5% to entitle a strain as a novel genus (Rossi-Tamisier, Benamar et al. 2015).

2.6 DNA extraction of axenic culture

Centrifugation of grown liquid methanotrophic (axenic) culture was carried out at 15000 rpm for 20 minutes. Or, axenic methanotrophic colonies grown on petri-plates were scrapped under aseptic conditions. Further purity check of the resulted pellet was carried out by streaking on 1/10th diluted nutrient agar plate. DNA extraction of biomass was carried out using a modified Gram-negative process of GenElute™ Bacterial Genomic DNA Kit Protocol (Sigma Aldrich, USA) (<https://www.sigmaaldrich.com/IN/en/product/sigma/na2110>).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Enrichment, Isolation, and Identification

Different coloured colonies such as neon pink or orange to yellow appeared on solid media plates after 3-4 weeks of incubation. A total of 7 strains were cultivated from Type I methanotrophs, while two of the strains were found to be novel strains. Five strains, FWC1, FWC2, WWC1, WWC3, and WWC5, showed 99% 16S rRNA similarity with *Methylomonas koyamae* JCM 16701 and will not be discussed further. Strain FWC3 was found to be a novel genus and documented earlier (Rahalkar, Khatri et al. 2020). Strain WWC4 was a putative novel species of the genus *Methylomonas* and showed 96.62% *pmoA* gene similarity with *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T.

3.2 Microscopic Identification

Strain WWC4 formed obedient orange-coloured colonies on the NMS media plate with 2% agarose as a solidifying agent (Figure 1). The diameter of the colonies was 2-4 mm. The live cells were thick short motile rods of 2.5-3 µm long and 0.8-1.2 µm (Figure 1). This strain formed a thin pinkish-orange turbid-biofilm on the top of the liquid-NMS media with methane and air (20:80) as headspace gas (Figure 1). Strain WWC4 showed a Gram-negative character.

3.3 Phylogenetic and Phylogenomic Affiliation

3.3.1 Functional *pmoA* gene: Based on the phylogenetic affiliation of the *pmoA* gene of strain WWC4, it showed ~99.5% similarity to a not yet to be valid species of *Methylomonas* genus (strain R-45383); and ~99.1% similarity with *Methylomonas* sp. R4F (not valid yet) and clone KID41_32 (Figure 2). *Methylomonas* sp. R-45383 was isolated from wetland (Ghent, Belgium) and has not been described and validated yet (Heylen, De Vos et al. 2016). While *Methylomonas* sp. R4F was isolated from peatland plants (Poleski National Park, Poland) and also has not been described and validated (Stępniewska, Goraj et al. 2017). When the *pmoA* gene of WWC4 was compared with the valid species of genus *Methylomonas*, it grouped with *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T and *Methylomonas koyamae* Fw12E-Y^T (Figure 2).

3.3.2 Universal 16S rRNA gene: The maximum likelihood tree of the 16S rRNA gene of strain WWC4 showed that the nearest neighbour is *Methylomonas koyamae* Fw12E-Y^T with 97.81% similarity, followed by *Methylomonas rhizoryzae* GJ1^T and *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T with 96.48% and 96.32% similarity, respectively (Figure 3).

3.3.3 Phylogenomic tree: The genomic comparison of the genome of strain WWC4 with its closest members of the genus *Methylomonas* was carried out using the PATRIC webserver. The phylogenomic tree of strain WWC4 showed that it grouped with *Methylomonas rhizoryzae* GJ1^T and *Methylomonas koyamae* Fw12E-Y^T (Figure 4).

3.4 Draft Genome Features

The genome of strain WWC4 was sequenced using Illumina sequencing technology, which produced a total of 23,037,313 paired-end reads with average read length distribution of 141 bp and quality score distribution of 36. The 21,606,919 high-quality paired-end reads were retained after low-quality bases and adapter sequence filtration using Trimmomatic (*v 0.35*) and cutadapt (*v 1.18*). A total of 73 High-quality reads were assembled using the Soapdenovo assembler. A total of 56 scaffolds of >500 bp were constructed, with an *N50* of 223 kb. The largest scaffold assembled measured 691.7 kb. The G+C content of the draft genome was

55.9%, and the genome contains 4,672 CDS (Table 1). A total of 4,559 genes were annotated using BlastX (Table 1). These ~56 contigs which belong to the genus *Methylomonas* were uploaded in RAST (<http://rast.nmpdr.org/>) and NCBI-PGAP for genome annotation (Table 1).

Genome-based comparison: The genomic comparison of strain WWC4 with genomes of its closest members was analysed to calculate the average nucleotide identity (ANIb-G, <http://jspecies.ribohost.com/jspeciesws/#analyse>), digital DNA–DNA hybridisation (dDDH, <http://ggdc.dsmz.de/>) and the average amino-acid identity (AAI, <http://enve-omics.ce.gatech.edu/aai/>). The nearest member of *Methylomonas* sp. WWC4 is *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1 with 74.48%, 74.76%, and 20.7 [18.5-23.2%] of AAI, ANIb, and DDH values, respectively (Table 2).

3.5 Salient metabolic characteristics predicted from the draft genome

The complete detail of enzymes related to the carbon metabolism of strain WWC4 has provided in Supplementary Table 1. Strain WWC4 contained two sets of particulate methane monooxygenase and one set of soluble methane monooxygenase for the oxidation of methane to methanol. The oxidation of methanol into formaldehyde was pursued by the presence of the methanol dehydrogenase enzyme present in the genome. Three copies of the PQQ-dependent dehydrogenase enzyme were present in the genome, out of which one of the enzymes was novel to methanotrophs and showed the closest similarity to *Gemmatimonadetes bacterium*. One copy of each NAD(P)-, zinc, and iron-dependent methanol dehydrogenases was also found in the genome of strain WWC4. All sets of enzymes for formaldehyde to formate and formate to carbon-dioxide conversion were present in the genome (Supplementary Table 1). The delta subunit of formate dehydrogenase was novel to methanotrophs and showed the closest similarity to *Bradyrhizobium algeriense* RST91.

The details of nitrogen metabolism pathway genes present in the WWC4 genome has provided in Supplementary Table 1. The genes required for environmental nitrogen fixation were found

in strain WWC4. The nitrogen fixation proteins NifT, X, Q, Z, W, and NifM, were found in the genome. One putative nitrogen fixation protein was also found in the genome of strain WWC4. The presence of classical nitrogenase molybdenum-iron proteins (NifD, K, H) was also detected in the genome. Nitrite reductase, nitrate reductase, and nitric oxide reductase were present in the genome (Supplementary Table 1).

Other vital proteins, such as proteins involved in hemerythrin metabolism, has provided in Supplementary Table 1. Hemerythrin genes are essential in oxygen scavenging conditions and helpful in transporting oxygen to particulate methane monooxygenase (Kao, Wang et al. 2008, Ross and Rosenzweig 2017, Rahalkar and Bahulikar 2018).

3.6

3.6 Physiology and chemotaxonomy

Methane and methanol can only be utilized by strain WWC4 as carbon sources. This strain cannot utilise multicarbon (0.1%) such as glucose, fructose, sucrose, maltose, xylose, arabinose, and raffinose. Neither formate nor formaldehyde was utilized by strain WWC4. It can tolerate up to 0.5% of methanol present in the growth media. The concentration of 0.05% of ammonium chloride, glutamate, peptone, yeast extract, and lysine can be used as a nitrogen source. It also possesses the ability to fix environmental nitrogen when growing optimally in nitrogen-free media. Strain WWC4 was a mesophilic methanotroph to grow in the 15-28°C temperature range with an optimum 25°C at a pH range of 3-9 under a buffered medium. It can tolerate up to 1% of NaCl-salinity in the medium. The comparisons of some of the major characteristics of strain WWC4 with other members of the *Methylomonas* genus are enlisted in Table 3 (Bowman 2015, Zhu, Cheng et al. 2020).

The cell wall fatty acids profile of strain WWC4 enclosed maximum amounts of 15:1 ω8c (21.09%), 16:0 3 OH (15.7%), and 16:1 ω5c (12.6%). The detail of the cell wall fatty acids

profile of strain WWC4 and type strains of species of the *Methylomonas* genus has provided in Table 4 (Bowman 2015, Zhu, Cheng et al. 2020).

4. Description of *Methylomonas sedimenticola* sp. nov. strain WWC4

A putative novel methanotroph strain WWC4 was isolated from a mud sample of a shallow freshwater part of a wetland of freshwater creek region, Alibag, near Nagaon beach, Maharashtra, India (18°26'30"N 72°54'20"E). Strain WWC4 showed 97.81% 16S rRNA similarity with *Methylomonas koyamae* Fw12E-Y^T and 96.62% *pmoA* gene similarity with *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T. The genomic comparison with closest members showed *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T with 74.48%, 74.76%, and 20.7 [18.5-23.2%] of AAI, ANI_b, and DDH values, respectively, with its closest member *Methylomonas methanica* FJG1^T. The genomic evaluation and phylogenetic analysis concluded the WWC4 strain was a putative novel methanotroph species. This putative novel species was isolated from a muddy-water sample and was phylogenetically related to the *Methylomonas* genus; therefore, the name is tentatively proposed as a *Methylomonas sedimenticola* sp. nov. strain WWC4.

Like almost all the methanotrophs, this strain WWC4 can only utilise methane and methanol as a carbon source. The RuMP and serine pathway can be used for methane oxidation, and the presence of genes for the same was found in its genomes. While the nitrogen source, ammonium chloride, glutamate, peptone, yeast extract, and lysine can be used to grow the strain, the environmental nitrogen can be fixed by strain WWC4, and it has been checked by laboratory experiments as well as the presence of genes in the genome. The carbon metabolic pathway contains two novel proteins. The novel PQQ-dependent dehydrogenase enzyme shows the closest similarity to the *Gemmatimonadetes bacterium*. The novel delta subunit of formate dehydrogenase shows the closest similarity to *Bradyrhizobium algeriense* RST91.

Methylomonas sedimenticola sp. nov. strain WWC4 is a mesophilic methanotroph and grew in a 15-28°C temperature range at a 3-10 pH range. The optimum temperature and pH were 25°C and 6.8, respectively. The major fatty acids were 15:1 ω 8c (21.09%), 16:0 3 OH (15.7%), and 16:1 ω 5c (12.6%). The whole-genome shotgun project was deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank, and the accession number is JAATWI0.1. The maintenance of strain WWC4 was done in our house WDCM approved culture collection, MACS collection of microorganisms, as MCMB-1474.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: KK and MCR. Data Analysis: MCR and KK. Experimental work: Strain isolation, characterization, maintenance and growth experiments: KK, and JM. Fund acquisition: MCR. Writing of the manuscript: KK. Writing-review and editing: MCR and KK. Final version reviewed and approved by all the authors.

Figure 1: Morphological character of strain WWC4: A, Live cells were observed under a phase-contrast microscope (Nikon 80i, Japan microscope with a camera) under 100X magnifications with oil emulsion; B, fixed and processed culture were observed under a Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Zeiss model EVO-MA-15 SEM); C, colony morphology; D, Growth in liquid medium.

Figure 2: Functional *pmoA* gene-based phylogenetic tree of strain WWC4 with its closest members. The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the *pmoA* sequence of WWC4 in comparison with the *pmoA* gene using MEGA X software (Kumar, Stecher et al. 2018). It was inferred by the Maximum Likelihood method and Poisson correction model (Tamura and Nei 1993). The bar shows a 0.2% divergence.

Figure 3: 16S rRNA gene phylogenetic tree of strain WWC4 with its closest members. The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the 16S rRNA sequence of WWC4 in comparison with 16S rRNA of type strains of valid species using MEGA X software (Kumar, Stecher et al. 2018). It was inferred by the Maximum Likelihood method and Tamura-Nei model (Tamura and Nei 1993). The bar shows a 2% divergence.

Figure 4: Phylogenomic tree of strain WWC4 with the genome of neighbour members. The tree was constructed using the PATRIC webserver (<https://www.patricbrc.org/>).

Kumar S, Stecher G, Li M, Knyaz C, Tamura K (2018) MEGA X: molecular evolutionary genetics analysis across computing platforms *Molecular biology and evolution* 35:1547-1549

Tamura K, Nei M (1993) Estimation of the number of nucleotide substitutions in the control region of mitochondrial DNA in humans and chimpanzees *Molecular biology and evolution* 10:512-526

Table 1: Draft genome details of strain WWC4

Draft genome traits	WWC4
NCBI Accession number	JAATWI0.1
Bio-project number	PRJNA520977
Bio-sample	SAMN10613771
Assembly	ASM1188220v1
Genome size	5.19 Mbp
G+C content	55.9%

N50	161,891 bp
Genes	4,560
Proteins	4,407
tRNA, nc RNA	39, 4
rRNA	2
Contigs	56

Table 2: AAI, ANIb, & DDH calculation of strain WWC4 with its closely related members

Closely related members	AAI value	ANIb value	dDDH value
<i>Methylomonas</i> sp. WWC4	-	-	-
<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> FJG1	74.48%	74.76%	20.7 [18.5-23.2%]
<i>Methylomonas koyamae</i> Fw12E-Y	74.45%	75.72%	21.5 [19.3-23.9%]
<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> S1	74.37%	74.77%	20.6 [18.4-23.1]
<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> NCIMB 11130	74.17%	74.76%	20.6 [18.4-23%]
<i>Methylomonas</i> sp. Kb3	74.15%	74.83%	21.6 [19.4-24%]
<i>Methylomonas rhizoryzae</i> GJ1	69.06%	72.58%	21.3 [19-23.7%]

Table 3: Comparison of the growth and other characteristics of strain WWC4 compared to other members of the *Methylomonas* genus

Characteristics	Strain WWC4	<i>Methylomonas methanica</i>	<i>Methylomonas koyamae</i>	<i>Methylomonas rhizoryzae</i> GJ1	<i>Methylomona s</i> sp. Kb3	<i>Methylomona s paludis</i>	<i>Methylomonas lenta</i>
Cell Morphology	Rods	Rods	Rods	Rods	Coccobacilli	Rods	Rods
Cell size	2.5-3 µm X 0.8-1.2 µm	0.5-3 µm X 0.5-1 µm	1.2-2.5 µm X 0.8-1.1 µm	0.6–1.0 µm X 0.7–2.3 µm	1-2 µm X 0.5- 1 µm	1-4 µm X 1-1.5 µm	1.3-2 µm X 0.6-0.9 µm
Motility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Surface pellicle	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Not detected
Pigmentation	Pink to orange	Pink to orange	Pink to orange	Pink	Pink to orange	Pale pink	White to pink sheen
Optimum growth temperature (°C)	25 (range 15-30°C)	25-30 (range 10-35)	30 (range 10-40)	25-33 (range 16-37)	25-30	20-25 (range 8-30)	20-25 (range 15-28)
Optimum pH	6.8 (range 3-10)	7 (range 5.5-9)	6.5 (range 5.5-7)	6-8 (range 5.5-8.5)	6.5-7	5-8-6.4 (range 3.8-7.3)	6.8-7.3 (range 6.3-7.8)
G+C Content	55.9%	51-54%	57%	53.87%	51.8%	48-49%	47%
Major PLFAs	15:1 ω8c, 16:0 3OH	C14:0, C16:1 ω8c	C14:0, C16:1 ω8c	C16:1, C14:0	C14:0, C16:1 ω5c	C16:1 ω5t, C16:1 ω8c	C16:1 ω8c, C16:1 ω5c

Methylomonas koyamae Type strain: Fw12E-Y, JCM 16701, NBRC 105905, NCIMB 14606;

Methylomonas lenta Type strain: R-45377, LMG 26260, JCM 19378;

Methylomonas methanica Type strain: ACM 3307, ATCC 35067, IMET 10543, NCIMB 11130, VKM B-2110.

Table 4: Cell wall fatty acids profile of strain WWC4 and type strains of species of the *Methylomonas* genus (in %)

Fatty acids	Strain WWC4	<i>Methylomonas methanica</i> <i>Methylomonas aurantiaca</i> <i>Methylomonas fodinarum</i>	<i>Methylomonas koyamae</i>	<i>Methylomonas rhizoryzae</i> GJ1	<i>Methylomonas lenta</i>	<i>Methylomonas paludis</i>	<i>Methylomonas</i> sp. Kb3
9:0	0.81	-	-	-	-	-	-
10:0	1.24	-	-	-	-	-	-
11:0	1.52	-	-	-	-	-	-
12:0	3.20	-	-	0.53	0.6-2.5	-	2.13
12:0 aldehyde	1.91	-	-	-	-	-	-
13:0	2.12	-	-	0.05	0.6-0.9	-	-
14:0	9.99	18.9-24.6	23	20.2	6.4-9.8	11.8	46.1
15:0	-	0-1.2	1.2	-	5.3-5.8	0.5	-
15:0 iso	-	0-2.5	-	-	-	-	-
15:0 anteiso	-	0-2.4	-	-	-	-	-
14:1 ω5c	4.23	-	-	-	-	-	-
15:1 ω8c	21.09	-	-	-	1.0-2.3	-	-
15:1 ω6c	3.04	-	-	-	0.5-0.6	-	-
15:1 ω5c	7.34	-	-	-	1.0-1.1	-	-
16:0	5.22	4.3-8.7	7.7	6.37	5.0	5.6	14.3
16:1ω11c	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16:1ω8c	-	18.7-41.3	39.4	-	40.8-42.4	22.1	-
16:1ω7c	-	7.7-15.3	4.35	-	9.1-10.5	13.9	-
16:1ω6c	-	4.5-13.3	-	-	-	5.0	-

16:1 ω 7c/ ω 6c (sum)	8.55	-	-	54.42	-	-	-
16:1 ω 5c	12.60	1.9-6.3	16.7	16.33	11.7-18.3	1.8	17.8
16:1 ω 5t	-	7.9-16.6	-	-	-	34.8	-
17:0 cyclo	-	0-2.1	-	-	-	-	-
17:1 ω 8c	-	-	-	-	0-0.8	-	-
17:1 ω 7c	-	0-0.7	-	-	-	-	-
17:1 ω 7t	-	0-0.3	-	-	-	-	-
18:0	-	0-0.1	0.72	-	-	1.2	-
18:1 ω 7c	-	0.2-2.5	-	-	-	-	2.02
18:1 ω 6c	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.32
18:1 ω 5c	-	0-0.2	1.7	-	-	-	-
19:0 cyclo	-	0.2-0.4	-	-	-	-	-
19:1 branched	-	0-0.5	-	-	-	-	-
10:0 3 OH	1.44	-	-	-	-	-	-
15:0 2 OH	-	-	1.43	-	-	-	-
16:0 3 OH	15.70	-	3.8	1.68	4.1-4.2	-	12.9

Compliance with ethical standards

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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